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3.11. Gender difference results in increase in adolescent smoking in 2019 in Ireland- European trend analysis of current smoking prevalence 1995-2019

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We examine trends in 30-day smoking among adolescents in Ireland and Europe, 1995-2020.

Ireland has participated in seven data collection waves of ESPAD (European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs) between 1995 and 2019, during which time more than 500,000 students have completed questionnaires on substance use, including cigarettes.

In 2019, some 100,000 students participated in ESPAD. In Ireland, 1967 students, born in 2003, were surveyed from a stratified random sample of 50 Irish schools.

We compared prevalence and gender differences in the Irish and European samples at different time points from 1995 to 2019.

In Ireland and across Europe, total prevalence of 30-day smoking decreased significantly between 1995 and 2019. Ireland's decrease (from 41% to 14%) was more dramatic than the European average (32% to 20%). Ireland's current prevalence is lower than the European average. However, while there was a decline of 5% in the European average between 2015 and 2019, Ireland's decreasing trend reversed, accounted for by an increase in male smoking from 13% to 16%.

In Ireland, smoking prevalence in 15-16-year-olds has increased for the first time in 25 years. Further focused action is urgently needed to achieve a prevalence of 5% by 2025.

Conflicts of interest: None

Figure 1: 30-day cigarette use since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

3.12. Standardising the Delivery of High Flow Nasal Oxygen on a Respiratory Ward

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High flow nasal oxygen (HFNO) is used to treat patients with hypoxic respiratory failure.^(1,2) HFNO use must be accompanied by forward planning in terms of whether escalation to critical care is appropriate.⁽¹⁾ HFNO is usually initiated by junior doctors, and we had observed that in this patient group, less than 50% of had an escalation plan determined within 24 hours.

Our aim was to promote HFNO awareness, provide educational sessions, design a proforma with emphasis on escalation planning, and collate medical staff and patient feedback. We therefore designed a HFNO proforma which included indication, initiation and weaning, and to include an escalation plan timely countersigned by a respiratory consultant.

We achieved over 80% compliance in terms of use of our proforma indicating escalation planning was both established early and consultant led. This was discussed with the patient at the time. Feedback from the medical staff was positive. Although the majority of patients regarded HFNO comfortable, they were often unclear of its indication.

Promoting HFNO awareness and providing educational sessions resulted in a positive and sustained uptake of the proforma. This resulted in both earlier consultant led escalation planning and discussion with the patients and families. Feedback from educational sessions was positive.

References

- 1) O'Neill et al. 2017 'High Flow Nasal Oxygen (HFNO): Use and management for adult inpatients in secondary care'. BHSCT policy v1.0
- 2) Roca O, Riera J, Torres F, Masclans JR (2010) High-flow oxygen therapy in respiratory failure *Respiratory Care*;55(4), 408-413

3.13. Gallbladder polyps in patients receiving subcutaneous treprostinil therapy for Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension.

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Idiopathic pulmonary arterial hypertension (IPAH) is a devastating illness characterised by progressive pulmonary vascular remodelling, proliferation and obliteration. Prostacyclin therapy is a core component of treatment, as it exerts beneficial pulmonary vasodilatory, antiproliferative, anti-inflammatory and antiplatelet properties. Interestingly prostacyclin analogues are not specific for the prostacyclin (IP) receptor and bind additional prostanoid receptors; this is exemplified by treprostinil, which mediates its physiological effects via a combination of IP, prostaglandin E2 (EP2) and prostaglandin D1 receptors (1). Outside of the pulmonary vasculature, prostacyclin has diverse functions including a recognised role in gallbladder physiology (2).

In our centre, a total of 50 patients are currently prescribed exogenous prostacyclin therapy for pulmonary hypertension and 8 have recent gallbladder imaging. Gallbladder polyps were identified in 3 of these 8 cases (37.5%) and all of these received prolonged treprostinil (Remodulin) therapy (Table 1). These results are higher than anticipated, as studies have reported gallbladder polyp prevalence between 1.4 - 12% in the general population.

We describe three cases of incidental gallbladder polyps in patients with IPAH and hypothesize that treprostinil may be implicated in the formation of these gallbladder polyps, due to its specific effects on IP and EP2 receptors and the established role of prostanoids in gallbladder health and disease.

Conflicts of interest: None

Table 1

Clinical characteristics of three cases of asymptomatic gallbladder polyps in patients prescribed prostacyclin analogues for IPAH. *The patient in Case 3 was transitioned from subcutaneous treprostinil to IV epoprostenol in August 2019

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Patient characteristics			
Age	60	47	48
Gender	Female	Male	Female
BMI	22	25	20
Duration of IPAH (years)	17	18	16
NYHA	II	III	II
PH therapy	Sildenafil Macitentan	Sildenafil Macitentan	Sildenafil Ambrisentan